

Design and Verification of Visual Detection Algorithm for Mini LED Chip and Panel Defects

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To enhance the quality and speed of defect detection in Mini LED chip panels, we have focused our research on defect detection methods using vision algorithms and strategies for algorithm acceleration. This paper introduces detection methods based on threshold segmentation and dynamic threshold segmentation, and constructs an improved algorithm architecture by combining the advantages of both. Threshold segmentation is suitable for detecting targets with significant contrast differences from the background, whereas dynamic threshold segmentation can detect defects with less obvious contrast. Additionally, for the high-speed design of the algorithm, the use of parallel computing through threading can effectively reduce computation time. Since Mini LED chip panels typically require high-resolution vision systems, which increase the time required for image acquisition and processing, a slicing algorithm is designed to reduce image size and thus improve speed. Furthermore, CUDA acceleration strategies can further enhance the processing speed. Finally, chip alignment experiments are conducted on a multi-degree-of-freedom spatial pose adjustment system to verify the feasibility of the vision algorithm as a feedback adjustment method.

CCS CONCEPTS • **Computing methodologies** • **Computer graphics** • **Image manipulation** • **Image processing**

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Mini LED, Defect detection, Speed optimization.

1 INTRODUCTION

Currently, there are several technical challenges that need to be overcome in Mini LED displays, such as developing mass production processes, low-cost integration technologies for large-scale production, and the integration of resources and capital. Additionally, issues such as high-speed, high-yield mass transfer, bonding, and color uniformity are also urgent problems that need to be addressed.^[1]

For the repair process of Mini LED chips, it is necessary to achieve rapid and high-precision visual positioning detection, and transmit the location information of the identified defective chips to the motion control system. The motion platform is then driven to the designated position, where lasers or other techniques are used to achieve the purpose of repair, thus completing the repair process. As a core component of the equipment, the visual inspection module faces key technical challenges such as defective chip recognition and high-speed, high-precision chip positioning, and there is an urgent need for technological breakthroughs in these areas. Yu Zhang ^[2] proposed a method for detecting Mura defects in panels by using a binary polynomial to perform surface fitting on the pixel coordinate space to construct a panel background model. Then, based on the characteristic of significant fitting errors between the areas where Mura defects are located and the background model, the defects can be detected. Zhiqiang Cai ^[3] eliminated the significant error points in the image by introducing the concept of limit error and established a standard background template. Then, he successfully performed difference segmentation on the pre-impregnated yarn defect images. In addition, when dealing with objects against complex backgrounds using the difference segmentation method^[4], image registration is also required to reduce the difficulty of false point filtering. The template matching method ^[5] is a fundamental and intuitive pattern recognition algorithm with the capability to perform localization and classification tasks. It operates based on the comparison of similarity between a normal image and a test image to determine whether the test image contains defects. Weng et al. ^[6] proposed an adaptive template method that utilizes Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) and Harris-Laplace methods to address the issue of poor fitting. Tsai et al. ^[7] introduced a dissimilarity method inspired by template matching for detecting surface defects of LED chips, which accommodates deviations and product variations. Teow Wee Teo and Mohd Zaid Abdullah ^[8] presented a detection method for micro-cracks in solar cells based on local texture analysis, achieving accurate detection of micro-cracks on solar cell surfaces through steps such as image preprocessing, local texture analysis, feature selection and classification, as well as post-processing and optimization. Yefan Zhou ^[9] proposed an image-based automatic surface defect detection algorithm for wafers, which combines image processing techniques with deep learning technologies to achieve high-precision defect detection.

Generally speaking, in order to improve detection accuracy, vision detection algorithms often sacrifice detection speed. To address the challenge of balancing detection speed and accuracy in Mini LED chip panel defect detection, this paper proposes a method that combines threshold segmentation with dynamic threshold segmentation to reduce false detection. It also employs sliced images along with thread pooling and CUDA acceleration strategies to ensure speed, and verifies the feasibility of alignment on mechanical equipment.

2 IMAGE PREPROCESS

The flowchart of the defect detection and localization algorithm is shown in Figure 1. , which yields the position information and other characteristics of defects and chips. The actual chip panel is shown in Figure 2. .

Figure 1. Flowchart of the algorithm

Figure 2. Actual MiniLED chip panel

2.1 Detection region extracting

The images captured by the camera may actually have boundary issues, and the redundant information contained in the boundaries can affect the detection efficiency of the algorithm. Therefore, it is necessary to remove the boundaries and extract the detection region of Interest for subsequent detection. The extraction effect is shown in Figure 3. , where the content within the red box is the target area.

Figure 3. Detection region of interest

2.2 Separating chips from the panel

In the initial image evaluation, due to the significant difference between the chip and the panel, threshold segmentation can be used to detect the chip; however, for panel defects, which have smaller differences compared to the panel, dynamic threshold segmentation algorithms yield better results. But when used in combination, dynamic threshold segmentation can lead to some false detection in the chip area, as shown in Figure 4. , where the red areas on the chip indicate false detection. In this paper, we separate the chip from the panel to reduce the occurrence of false detection, and the processing effect is shown in Figure 5. .

Figure 4. The effect of the dynamic threshold segmentation

Figure 5. The image of after separating

3 DEFECT DETECTION ALGORITHM

3.1 Chip defect detection

For the defect types existing on the chip, they are generally occlusion and dirt. The defect characteristics are quite different from the chip characteristics. The threshold segmentation can be done in the chip area, and the threshold segmentation formula is as following the formula 1:

$$dst(x,y) = \begin{cases} Specify, & src(x,y) > thread \\ 0, & src(x,y) < thread \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Figure 6. Chip detection

Where, $src(x, y)$ represents the grayscale value at (x, y) in the original image, $dst(x, y)$ represents the grayscale value at (x, y) after processing, $thread$ is a self-set grayscale, and $Specify$ is the designated grayscale value after processing. Figure 6. shows the effect of chip detection:

3.2 Panel Defect Detecting Method

The next subsections provide instructions on how to insert figures, tables, and equations in your document. There are many kinds of defects in the panel, but the gray value of the dotted defects is similar to the background gray value, which cannot be accurately detected by the threshold segmentation alone. By reproducing the dynamic threshold segmentation algorithm in Halcon combined with the median filtering, the threshold segmentation of local areas can be achieved, and the defects can be detected more accurately. The formula is as follows.

If $src(x, y) - mean(x, y) \geq offset$, following the formula 2, Otherwise, following the formula 3,

$$dst(x, y) = Specify \quad (2)$$

$$dst(x, y) = 0 \quad (3)$$

Where $src(x, y)$ represents the grayscale value at (x, y) in the original image, $mean(x, y)$ represents the grayscale value at (x, y) after median filtering, $dst(x, y)$ represents the grayscale value at (x, y) after processing, $offset$ is the compensation value, and $Specify$ is the designated grayscale value after processing. Figure 7. shows the effect of panel detection.

Figure 7. Panel detection

3.3 Image slicing and thread pooling

The camera captures images with a resolution of up to 65 million pixels, and the image size is (9344,7000), which results in excessively slow image processing times and fails to meet speed requirements. In this paper, we adopt the approach of dividing the image into multiple slices, converting the large-sized image into smaller ones, and processing these smaller images in parallel with multiple threads. The processing speed of a single small image is approximately equal to that of multiple small images, thereby significantly increasing the algorithm's speed. As shown in Figure 8, based on the extraction of the target area, we set the number of slices, currently using a (3,3) grid. Furthermore, parallel processing employs a thread pool method, which allows for self-adjustment of the number of threads, avoiding the cumbersome process of manual adjustment. Additionally, on top of this, we also utilize CUDA acceleration to further reduce detection time ^[10]. The core of

the CUDA acceleration strategy lies in leveraging the powerful computing capabilities of GPUs to accelerate various applications. GPUs have a large number of cores and are suitable for highly parallelized computing tasks. Therefore, the CUDA acceleration strategy can significantly improve computational efficiency.

Figure 8. Image slicing

Figure 9. thread pooling

4 EXPERIMENT AND ANALYSIS

4.1 The analysis of Algorithm

The algorithm verification experiment was conducted on Windows 10 with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8700 CPU and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 GPU, utilizing CUDA 11.0 for GPU acceleration. The final results are shown in Figure 10. Additionally, due to the poor quality of the images, quantitative analysis of the image detection effectiveness could not be performed. Instead, a qualitative analysis of the image detection effectiveness was conducted, as shown in Figure 11. , comparing the original image, Threshold segmentation image, dynamic threshold segmentation image, and the results obtained using the method presented in this paper. The detection speed could be quantitatively analyzed, as presented in Table 1.

Figure 10. Final result

Figure 11. Qualitative analysis and comparison

Table 1: Comparison table of quantitative analysis of speed

Hardware	Acceleration Method	Compilation mode	Execution Speed
OS:Windows 10 CPU: Intel(R) Core(TM) i7 8700 GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX3080	none	Debug	11089ms
	Image slicing and thread pooling	Debug	3582ms
		Release	1242ms
	Image slicing and thread pooling and CUDA	Release	338ms

4.2 The Results of experiment

Additionally, a set of simple alignment comparison experiments were conducted in a multi-degree-of-freedom spatial pose adjustment system to verify the effectiveness of vision-guided alignment. The system and its effects are shown in Figure 12. and Figure 13.

Figure 12. Experimental system.(1) X-axis Linear motor,(2) Industrial camera,(3) lens, (4) Gantry Y1 axis linear motor, (5) Gantry Y2 axis linear motor, (6) Chip panel, (7) Rotating lifting platform, (8) Loading conveyor belt

Figure 13. Comparison of Detection Effects Before and After Applying Visual Localization Algorithm.(a)before,(b)after

5 CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a defect detection algorithm for Mini LED chips, which currently processes an image of size (9377,7000) in 338ms and completes chip position alignment verification on a multi-degree-of-freedom spatial pose adjustment system. Addressing current challenges in chip image detection, such as weak defect detection, elimination of irrelevant factors, and speed optimization, the paper presents corresponding solutions. The slicing algorithm and thread pool significantly enhance detection efficiency, and with the CUDA acceleration strategy, the detection speed is increased from 11089ms to 338ms. For separate detection of panels and chips, threshold segmentation is applied to handle high-contrast chip defects, while dynamic threshold segmentation are used for low-contrast panel defects, substantially improving defect detection capabilities. Finally, the algorithm is applied to alignment equipment for visual feedback comparison experiments, successfully verifying its feasibility.

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